

Synthesis of new 1-(phthalimido)substituted-aziridine-2-carboxylates

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Synthesis of new *N*-amidoaziridines by using aziridinating reagent, *N*-aminophthalimide (1) has been reported. The intermediate generated in the lead tetraacetate oxidation (1) is not the *N*-nitrene (2) but *N*-acetoxyphthalimide (3) which brings about aziridination of olefins.

Aziridines possess various biological activities¹. Out of several methods of synthesis of aziridines², the addition of nitrene to alkenes can not be regarded as a preparative method because the highly reactive and unselective behaviour of nitrenes usually leads to the mixture of the products. This is due to the fact that the interconversion of triplet states leads to the loss of stereospecificity during the addition to alkenes³. However, the oxidation of the corresponding *N*-aminophthalimide gives thermodynamically more stable *trans*-isomer.

The reaction of *N*-aminophthalimide with LTA in presence of electron-deficient as well as electron-rich

olefins gives *N*-amidoaziridines with high stereospecificity⁴. The intermediate in the lead tetraacetate oxidation of phthalimide at -30° is *N*-acetoxyphthalimide (3).

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-470 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

Scheme 1

olefins gives *N*-amidoaziridines with high stereospecificity⁴. The intermediate in the lead tetraacetate oxidation of phthalimide at -30° is *N*-acetoxyphthalimide (3).

Table 1. M.p. data of alkyl 1-(phthalimido)-3-substituted-aziridine-2-carboxylate (4a-r)*

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	M.p. °C
4a	CH ₃	H	H	COOCH ₃	159
b	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	COOCH ₃	185
c	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	187
d	C ₆ H ₅	H	CH ₃	COOCH ₃	188
e	C ₆ H ₅	H	CH ₃	COOC ₂ H ₅	146
f	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃	COOCH ₃	181
g	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	176
h	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	COOCH ₃	189
i	<i>p</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	H	COOCH ₃	148
j	<i>p</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	161
k	<i>p</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	CH ₃	COOC ₂ H ₅	183
l	<i>p</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	H	COOCH ₃	165
m	<i>p</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	150
n	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	H	H	COOCH ₃	169
o	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	H	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	184
p	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	H	COOCH ₃	190
q	3,4-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	H	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	155
r	H	H	H	CH ₂ -S(CH ₃) ₃	95

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Alkyl-1-(phthalimido)-2,3-dimethylaziridine-2-carboxylate (4b): Lead tetraacetate (0.001 mol) was added to a suspension of 1 (0.001 mol) in dry dichloromethane (5 ml) at -30° and the mixture was stirred for 15 min. Then ethyl 3,3-dimethylacrylate (0.001 mol) was added to it with stirring and the mixture was allowed to warm at 25° and filtered. The filtrate was washed successively with saturated sodium hydrogen carbonate solution (5 ml) and water (2 ×

5 ml). The solution was dried and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residue was purified by column chromatography using a solvent system ethyl acetate-hexane (30 : 70) as an eluent to furnish **4b** (61%), ν_{\max} 1760 (C=O ester), 1680 (C=O amido), 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 1.6 (3H, s, CH_3 *trans* to ester), 1.76 (3H, s, CH_3 *cis* to ester), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH_3 ester), 7–7.5 (4H, m, ArH); m/z 274 (1), 162 (46), 147 (80), 132 (8), 119 (5), 104 (100), 91 (11), 76 (83). Similarly other compounds were prepared (yields 58–70%) (Table 1).

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